

ANTECEDENT FACTORS OF SUCCESS IN MANAGEMENT OF TRAINING CENTERS IN THAILAND

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Abstract

The training centers are created to respond to the business needs of various organizations for efficient development of their human resource to equip them with knowledge, ability, skills and experience that can be applied to upgrade the potential of both the personnel and the organization in both the state sector and private sector work agencies. Therefore, the training centers in the business market must be adjusted to change in accordance with the needs of consumers. At present, a lot of training center businesses has occurred resulting in high competition. The training center administrators cannot create advantages in the competition, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic. As a result, the training centers face more business operation problems caused by the lack of competitive competency. The objectives of this research are as follows: (1) to study levels of the self-improvement intention, the 7Ps marketing strategy, the potential of resource persons, the image of the training site, and quality of the training program affecting the success in management of training centers in Thailand; (2) to study the influences of the self-improvement intention, the 7Ps marketing strategy, the potential of resource persons, the image of the training site, and quality of the training program affecting the success in management of training centers in Thailand; and (3) to create a model of success in management of training centers in Thailand. This study is a mixed-method research involving the quantitative and qualitative research methodologies. In the quantitative study, the research sample consisted of 420 trainees in private training centers in Thailand, obtained by multi-stage sampling. The sample size was determined based on the criterion of 20 times of the observable variables. A questionnaire was employed as the data collecting instrument. The data were analyzed using the structural equation modeling analysis. In the qualitative study, the researcher conducted in-depth interviews of target group persons consisting of 20 administrators and experts on management of training centers in Thailand. The research findings indicated that (1) the self-improvement intention, the 7Ps marketing strategy, the potential of resource persons, the image of the training site, quality of the training program, and the success in management of training centers in Thailand were rated at the high level; (2) the self-improvement intention, the 7Ps marketing strategy, the potential of resource persons, the image of the training site, and quality of the training program had influences on the success in management of training centers in Thailand, which were at the .05 level of statistical significance; and (3) the model of success in management of training centers in Thailand, developed by the researcher, was named as PISQIL Model (P = Lecturer's Potential, I = Self-Improvement Intention, S = 7Ps Marketing Strategy, Q = Course Quality, I = Training Site Image, L = Customer Loyalty). In addition, results of the qualitative study indicated that in order to create the success of management of training centers in Thailand, the administrators should make a comprehensive study of the problems and trends of the needs of the target group that would lead to the creation of the program consistent with the needs for efficient development of the personnel of each organization. The results of this research can be adjusted to apply as guidelines for formulation of policies concerning the management of training centers in order to promote the sustainable success in the management of training centers in Thailand in the future.

Keywords: Antecedent factor / success in management of training center /Thailand

INTRODUCTION

Organizations that want to be successful in the competition have developed human resources to be effective in terms of knowledge, competence, skills and experience that bring more marketing advantages. Training and development of personnel in the organization is therefore necessary and must be carried out continuously for the ability to achieve higher goals all the time (Nguyen & Duong, 2020). In such a situation, organizations around the world are striving for prosperity and defeat those in the same industry. To do so, organizations must source and use human resources efficiently. Every organization consequently needs to be more vigorous in keeping its human resources up-to-date. Managers, as a result, need to pay special attention to all the core functions of human resource management because they have different roles in the organization. The collective perception and economy among others influences the management of organizational goals and makes the organization prosper continuously in the market. One of the main functions of human resource management is to train employees in the organization which is one way to prepare and increase sustainable performance (Álvarez-Álvarez & Arnáiz-Uzquiza, 2017).

Nowadays, training centers have emerged to meet the needs of businesses in developing more human resources. Both the public and private sectors compete in the market of training center business that adapts to the needs of consumers, both the normal form that provides services in the actual space in the training center and digital training form that can meet the needs of the participants in each organization limitlessly. In the government sector, the 25 labor skill development centers have been established throughout the country by the Ministry of Labor. Nevertheless, with the need for human resource development of each organization at present, there are more private training center businesses came into the market, making it highly competitive, especially training centers of the private sector.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Training Site Image. There are several important expectations for customers attending the Training Center, such as having enough parking spaces, welcoming upon registration, taking care, lounges, training rooms, food, cleanliness, comfort and courtesy of all staff in welcoming including all materials and equipment related to training. (Nguyen & Duong, 2020. These are an overview that can satisfy the participants in all dimensions (Mohammed, 2018) because these are the images that can build loyalty among the participants such as word of mouth and re-entering the service when the next training is needed. (Owusu, M.A., 2020) suggested that training site image affects customers' decision making to choose a training site. It is a marketing strategy that creates a good image for the trainees and can create motivation for training which has a positive effect on training, including creating value and increasing the dignity of employees in receiving training (Ocen, Francis & Angundaru, 2017; Álvarez-Álvarez & Arnáiz-Uzquiza, 2017).

7Ps marketing strategy. It refers to marketing mix that consists of products, which means training courses, prices and venues for training are appropriate and have complete training materials. Promotion, discounts or rewards to trainees in a variety of ways and expert trainers

can satisfy trainees (Tabiu, Pangil & Othman, 2018). Physical evidence and other important components of training can impress the participants. The step-by-step process of organizing the training affects the success of training center through customer loyalty. (Kuncoro & Sutomo (2018) describes the 7Ps marketing strategy as what fosters business success through customer loyalty. These include product, price, place, promotion, people, physical evidence, and processes, helping to increase customer loyalty and business success. (Babu & Masthanvali, 2017).

Lecturer potential. Specialized knowledge and ability of trainers from training centers has efficiency in transferring knowledge in the subject being trained and having fun training. It can create a learning atmosphere that makes the trainees happy throughout the training period and the training center successful with the loyalty of the participants by recommending, referring, repeating the training in the next course and not changing their mind to train in other training centers. (Mdhlalose, 2020) discussed the potential of the lecturer as it is what the trainees are interested in after the training course because it can affect training and development as well as the operation of the organization. Training and development have a positive effect on the performance of employees in the department and efficiency of the organization. The lecturer potential affects the perception and efficiency of the trainees.

Course Quality. In the self-improvement of trainees at various training centers, the first part that the trainees want and need is the quality of the curriculum. (Nguyen & Duong, 2020) They will consider the content and usefulness for improving operational skills, increasing knowledge and having more operational potential. (Diallo et al., 2018). After training, empirical results lead to the satisfaction and loyalty of the trainees towards training center, in turn state that course quality is a product to serve the trainees that must be able to meet the needs of customers and the market, use in many cases and see real results after training. (Darmawan, Mardikaningsih & Hadi, 2018; Famiyeh, Asante-Darko & Kwarteng, 2018). This is because the course is a factor that influences training effectiveness and it is an incentive for trainees to decide to choose the service (Yang, Fan, & Huang, 2017).

Self-improvement intention. For organizational operation to have progress and to be honored by the organization, most importantly, every employee should create their own value in order to benefit the organization. Therefore, both formal and informal self-improvement is an option for employees seeking career advancement Generally, in a business organization that requires competitive power and efficiency in business operations, training is often organized to increase knowledge, skills and experiences for employees to develop their operational potential. Internal management and inviting speakers to educate or bring employees to training in a training center are considered in terms of the needs of benefits for use. (Bapat, 2017). Training centers, therefore, need to provide courses and trainers with expertise in the subjects that customers want to train, which meets the needs and expectations of customers who intend to attend training in the training center. In addition, several scholars have defined the training intention of the client. (Gandhi, Sachdeva & Gupta, 2019). Haryonoa, Supardib & Udina (2020) has stated that the training intention is the aim of the trainees with the goal of utilizing job

promotion. This motivates work and has a positive impact on performance. Quality performance is a direct result of training. (Giovanis & Tsoukatos, 2017).

METHODOLOGY

In the research, the population was trainees in 23 registered and active private sector training centers in Thailand (Department of Business Development, 2021) and trainees from 243 private companies, a total of 266 places. To be able to determine the population in the study, the population of each training center was 100 participants, so the total population was 26,600 participants. Sample size was estimated from the observation variable in the ratio of 1 to 20. In this research, there were 21 observation variables. The researchers, thus, determined the sample size of 420 participants using multistage sampling from trainees in private training centers in Thailand.

Multistage sampling method was used as follows:

Step 1, training centers of the private sector in Thailand that are still operating according to the information found were divided into 2 groups: 23 training centers registered with the Department of Business Development (Department of Business Development, 2021) and 243 training centers from companies in the private sector, a total of 266 places. To obtain the population in the study, therefore, the researchers estimated the population of 100 participants per place, thus having a total population of 26,600 participants. Step 2, the researcher determined the sample who were trainees in private training centers in Thailand in proportion to each location: 36 participants from training centers registered with the Department of Business Development, 384 participants from the training centers from companies in the private sector, totaling 420 samples.

Quantitative research tool was a questionnaire. The 420 questionnaires were used to collect data from trainees in private training centers in Thailand. The questionnaire quality test was divided into 2 areas as follows: 1) Content validity, and 2) reliability. In data collection, the researchers coordinated with those involved in operation of private training centers in Thailand. The questionnaires were collected during the specified period of time. When receiving the questionnaire, the researchers checked the completeness of the questionnaires before processing and analyzing the data. The data were analyzed using structural equation modeling (SEM).

Table 1 Statistical test of empirical variables (n=420)

Variable	M	S.D.	%CV	Sk	Ku	χ^2	P-value
CNVT	3.45	1.02	29.57	-.855	-2.064	4.993	.082
CLEN	3.76	0.93	24.73	-1.612	-3.122	12.344	.002
PRPT	3.59	1.00	27.86	-1.336	-2.468	7.873	.020
PRDC	3.80	1.01	26.58	-2.520	-3.987	22.245	.000
PRIC	3.69	0.95	25.75	-1.488	-2.890	1.567	.005
LOCA	3.65	1.01	27.67	-1.713	-3.878	17.976	.000
PRMN	3.75	0.90	24.00	-1.367	-2.814	9.786	.007
PERN	3.83	1.03	26.89	-2.919	-4.217	26.299	.000
PHYS	3.81	0.98	25.72	-2.036	-6.854	51.120	.000
PROC	3.76	0.99	26.33	-1.990	-3.593	16.870	.000
EXPT	3.52	1.17	33.24	-1.852	-4.851	26.961	.000
TRMS	3.60	1.01	28.06	-1.530	-2.860	1.520	.005
FNTC	3.54	1.09	30.79	-1.815	-3.305	14.217	.001
MEMK	3.55	0.90	25.35	-.650	-1.545	2.808	.246
UTLY	3.61	0.87	24.10	-.228	-1.572	2.522	.283
EMPC	3.70	0.87	23.51	-.581	-2.479	6.484	.039
ICSK	3.56	1.04	29.21	-1.491	-2.861	1.409	.005
GOUS	3.74	0.98	26.20	-1.923	-3.682	17.252	.000
RETL	3.68	0.88	23.91	-.595	-3.741	14.350	.001
CMBC	3.61	0.99	27.42	-1.292	-2.584	8.347	.015
NOSW	3.53	0.98	27.76	-1.020	-2.025	5.141	.076

From the Table 1 of the testing results of the normal curve distribution or normal score of the observed variables in the structural equation model with chi-square (χ^2), it was found that the convenient (CNVT), meet market (MEMK), utility (UTLY), and no switching (NOSW) had no statistically significant level ($p > .05$). It showed that such variables had normal distribution. In addition, all other observed variables had statistically significant level ($p < .05$), indicating that such variables had non normal distribution. This may result in assessing the model fit. The chi-square (χ^2) was problematic, so the researchers solved the problem of the statistic in estimating fit by calculating the ratio of chi-square (χ^2) to degrees of freedom (df). If the value is less than 2.00, the model is fit to the empirical data, although the χ^2 of the model was statistically significant ($p\text{-value} < .05$) (Wanichbuncha, 2013; Hair, et al., 2006).

Table 2: Factor Loadings (n=420)

Variables	Factor Loading (λ)	Error (θ)	t	R ²
Training site image (IMAG)				
Convenient (CNVT)	.98	.05	27.56	.95
Cleanness (CLEN)	.65	.58	14.68	.42
Proportion (PRPT)	.83	.31	14.48	.69
$\rho_c = .87 \quad \rho_v = .69$				
7Ps marketing strategy (MARSG)				
Product (PRDC)	.86	.26	21.7	.74
Price (PRIC)	.82	.33	19.89	.67
Location (LOCA)	.86	.27	21.51	.73
Promotion (PRMN)	.83	.32	20.47	.68
Personnel (PERN)	.86	.27	21.26	.73
Physical Evidence (PHYS)	.80	.36	19.47	.64
Process (PROC)	.68	.54	15.41	.46
$\rho_c = .93 \quad \rho_v = .67$				
Lecturer's' potential (LECPT)				
Expertise (EXPT)	.81	.34	17.80	.66
Transmitting Skills (TRMS)	.68	.54	14.60	.46
Funny Teaching (FNTEC)	.84	.29	18.54	.71
$\rho_c = .82 \quad \rho_v = .61$				
Course quality (COUR)				
Meet Market (MEMK)	.77	.41	17.74	.59
Utility (UTLY)	.94	.12	23.39	.88
Empirical Results (EMPC)	.82	.33	19.24	.67
$\rho_c = .88 \quad \rho_v = .71$				
Self-improvement intention (SIINT)				
Increasing Work Skills (ICSK)	.98	.05	27.62	.95
Goal of Using (GOUS)	.72	.49	16.74	.51
$\rho_c = .84 \quad \rho_v = .73$				
Loyalty (LOYT)				
Recommending and Telling (RETL)	.71	.49	15.45	.51
Coming Back to Use Service (CMBC)	.91	.18	20.42	.82
No Switching (NOSW)	.75	.44	16.27	.56
$\rho_c = .83 \quad \rho_v = .63$				

From the table 2, training site image (IMAG) consisted of 3 factors. The standardized solution (λ) was equal to .65 - .98 with statistical significance at the .05 level. The standard error (θ) was equal to .05 - .58, able to explain the variance of the training site image (IMAG). Each variable had reliability by considering R² of 42-95%. The latent variable had the composite reliability (ρ_c) of .87 and average variable extracted (ρ_v) of .69.

7Ps marketing strategy (MARSG) consisted of 7 factors. The standardized solution (λ) was equal to .68 - .86 with statistical significance at the .05 level. The standard error (θ) was equal to .26-.54, able to explain the variance of 7Ps marketing strategy (MARSG). Each variable had

reliability by considering R^2 of 46-74%. The latent variable had the composite reliability (ρ_c) of .93 and average variable extracted (ρ_v) of .67.

Lecturer potential (LECPT) consisted of 3 factors. The standardized solution (λ) was equal to .68 to .84 with statistical significance at the .05 level. The standard errors (θ) was equal to .29-.54, able to explain the variance of lecturer potential (LECPT). Each variable had reliability by considering R^2 of 46 – 71%. The latent variable had the composite reliability (ρ_c) of .82 and average variable extracted (ρ_v) of .61. Course quality (COUR) consisted of 3 factors. The standardized solution (λ) was equal to .77 - .94 with statistical significance at the .05 level. The standard error (θ) was equal to .12-.41, able to explain the variance of course quality (COUR). Each variable had reliability by considering R^2 of 59-88%. The latent variable had the composite reliability (ρ_c) of .88 and average variable extracted (ρ_v) of .71. Self-improvement intention (SIINT) consisted of 2 factors. The standardized solution (λ) was equal to .72 - .98, with statistical significance at the .05 level. The standard error (θ) was equal to .05-.49, able to explain the variance of the self-improvement intention (SIINT). Each variable had reliability by considering R^2 of 51-95%. The latent variable had the composite reliability (ρ_c) of .84 and average variable extracted (ρ_v) of .73. Loyalty (LOYT) consisted of 3 factors. The standardized solution (λ) was equal to .71 - .91 with statistical significance at the .05 level. The standard error (θ) was equal to .18-.49, able to explain the variance of the Loyalty Variable (LOYT). Each variable had reliability by considering R^2 of 51 – 82%. The latent variable had a composite reliability (ρ_c) of .83 and average variable extracted (ρ_v) of .63

Table 3: Measurement Model (n=420)

Dependent variables	R^2	Effects	Independent variables				
			Self-improvement intention (SIINT)	Training site image (IMAG)	7Ps marketing strategy (MARSG)	Lecturer potential (LECPT)	Course quality (COUR)
self-improvement intention (SIINT)	.98	DE	-	.32*(2.68)	.41*(10.38)	.30*(4.11)	.46*(4.42)
		IE	-	-	-	-	-
		TE	-	.32*(2.68)	.41*(10.38)	.30*(4.11)	.46*(4.42)
Loyalty (LOYT)	.92	DE	.64*(6.59)	.31*(2.68)	.63*(4.53)	.65*(4.82)	.40*(4.29)
		IE	-	.42*(4.54)	.26*(4.57)	.23*(4.58)	.23*(4.37)
		TE	.64*(6.59)	.73*(4.99)	.89*(2.27)	.88*(4.44)	.63*(4.87)

$\chi^2 = 307.43$ df = 156 p-value = .00000, $\chi^2 / df = 1.97$, RMSEA = .048, RMR = .046, SRMR = .047, CFI = .98, GFI = .94, AGFI = .91, CN = 233.01

From the Table 3 and Figure 1, the adjusted structure equation model of self-improvement intention, 7Ps marketing strategy, lecturer potential, training site image and course quality affecting the success in management of training centers in Thailand was fit to empirical data at an acceptable level by considering fit indices as follows: $\chi^2 = 307.43$, df = 156 p-value = .00000, $\chi^2/df = 1.97$, RMSEA = .048, RMR = .046, SRMR = .047, CFI = .98, GFI = .94, AGFI = .91, CN = 233.01. The estimation in the structural equation model was as follows:

- 1) Training site image (IMAG) had a direct effect on self-improvement intention (SIINT), with a path coefficient of .32 and a statistically significant level of .05.
- 2) 7Ps marketing strategy (MARSG) had a direct effect on self-improvement intention (SIINT), with a path coefficient of .41 and a statistically significant level of .05.
- 3) Lecturer potential (LECPT) had a direct effect on self-improvement intention (SIINT), with a path coefficient of .30 and a statistically significant level of .05.
- 4) Course quality (COUR) had a direct effect on self-improvement intention (SIINT), with a path coefficient of .46 and a statistically significant level of .05.
- 5) Self-improvement intention (SIINT) had a direct effect on loyalty (LOYT), with a path coefficient of .64 and a statistically significant level of .05.
- 6) Training site image (IMAG) had a direct effect on loyalty (LOYT), with a path coefficient of .31 and a statistically significant level of .05.
- 7) 7Ps marketing strategy (MARSG) had a direct effect on loyalty (LOYT), with a path coefficient of .63 and a statistically significant level of .05.
- 8) Lecturer potential (LECPT) had a direct effect on loyalty (LOYT), with a path coefficient of .65 and a statistically significant level of .05.
- 9) Course quality (COUR) had a direct effect on loyalty (LOYT), with a path coefficient of .40 and a statistically significant level of .05.
- 10) Training site image (IMAG), 7Ps marketing strategy (MARSG), lecturer potential (LECPT), course quality (COUR) could jointly predict loyalty (LOYT) by 92%.

FIGURE 1. Adjust Model (n=420)

The result of adjusted structural equation model modified found that it was fit to the empirical data: $\chi^2 = 307.43$ $df = 156$ $p\text{-value} = .00000$, $\chi^2/df = 1.97$, $RMSEA = .048$, $RMR = .046$, $SRMR = .047$, $CFI = .98$, $GFI = .94$, $AGFI = .91$, $CN = 233.01$. The researchers therefore trusted the parameter estimates in the model and reported the equation that occurred in the model, both in the part of reporting the results of the equation and the measurement model, showing the factor loadings of observation variables on latent variables. In addition, the structural model depicted the relationship between latent variables themselves according to the research hypotheses.

CONCLUSION

The results on the levels of self-improvement intention, 7Ps marketing strategy, lecturer potential, training site image and course quality that affect the success in management of training centers in Thailand at a high level.

The path relationship between the independent variables and dependent variables in the developed and adjusted model showed that lecturer potential, self-improvement intention, 7Ps marketing strategy, course quality and training site image directly affected loyalty, with statistically significant level of .05, able to explain the variance by 92%.

The relationship path equations between the exogenous latent variables that have a total effect on the endogenous latent variables (Reduced equations) in the adjusted model showed that exogenous latent variables, including 7Ps marketing strategies, lecturer potential, training site image, had a total effect on loyalty, with statistically significant level of .05, able to explain the variance by 83%.

After obtaining the findings according to the research objectives, the researchers therefore developed the PISQIL Model (P = Lecturer potential, I = Self-Improvement Intention, S = 7Ps Marketing Strategy, Q = Course Quality, I = Training Site Image, L = Customer Loyalty) to be a model for success in management of training centers in Thailand in the future.

Policy recommendations

Policy recommendations are vital to the success in management of the training centers in Thailand. The researchers recommend the followings:

- 1) Government and private sectors should formulate a policy of cooperation with relevant organizations in all sectors in successful development of training center management in Thailand.
- 2) Relevant agencies should use findings to formulate policies and integrated plans to create success in running a training center for all target groups by promoting self-development intentions, 7Ps marketing strategy, lecturer potential, training site image and course quality to improve the efficiency of training center management in Thailand steadily.

Academic Recommendations and Implementations

From the research, there are findings that can be applied in academics and practices as follows:

- 1) Relevant agencies should use the findings to promote and develop academic matter for the success in managing training centers in Thailand.
- 2) The Ministry of Labor and the Ministry of Education, as well as the private sector and organizations that operate training centers in Thailand should support and promote the success of training center management in Thailand.
- 3) Governments, private sectors and related agencies should implement integrated actions for promoting self-improvement of the trainees, using 7Ps Marketing Strategy of entrepreneurs, selecting potential lecturers, creating an image of a training site, improving the quality of courses and managing training centers in Thailand for sustainable success.

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